

EDEN ISS

D1.2 - Data Management Plan

prepared for

WP 1.1 - Administrative & Technical Management

Version: 1.0

Published: 2015-07-23

Approved by:	Daniel Schubert	DLR	Work Package Leader
Approved by:	Matthew Bamsey	DLR	Systems Engineer
Approved by:	Daniel Schubert	DLR	Project Manager

List of Authors:

Participant No.	Short name	Author name(s)
1	DLR	M. Bamsey

Document Change Log:

Version	Date	Author name(s)	Description of Change
0.1	2015-06-12	See list of authors	Initial draft.
0.2	2015-07-01	M. Bamsey	Revised draft.
0.3	2015-07-09	M. Bamsey	General updates. Specific updates to project datasets with input from M. Bennett, G. Boscheri, T. Dueck, P. Zabel, DLR-ME. Added specific EDEN ISS Zenodo information.
1.0	2015-07-23	M. Bamsey	Minor updates. Official full release.

Executive summary

This document presents the data management plan of the EDEN ISS project.

Table of contents

Executive summary	3
Table of contents	4
Acronyms	5
1 General EDEN ISS data management guidelines	6
1.1 Linkages to relevant Horizon 2020 guidelines.....	6
1.2 Guideline distinctions between scientific publications and research data	6
1.3 Top-level EDEN ISS data management implementation	8
1.3.1 Expected project datasets	8
1.3.2 Standards and metadata	9
1.3.3 Data sharing	10
1.3.4 Archiving and preservation	11
2 Project datasets	13
2.1 Plant cultivation experiments and training dataset	13
2.1.1 Dataset description	13
2.1.2 Standards and metadata	13
2.1.3 Data sharing	14
2.1.4 Archiving and preservation	14
2.2 Mobile Test Facility operations dataset	14
2.2.1 Dataset description	14
2.2.2 Standards and metadata	14
2.2.3 Data sharing	15
2.2.4 Archiving and preservation	15
2.3 Full-rack demonstrator operations dataset	15
2.3.1 Dataset description	15
2.3.2 Standards and metadata	16
2.3.3 Data sharing	16
2.3.4 Archiving and preservation	16
2.4 Food quality and safety dataset	16
2.4.1 Dataset description	16
2.4.2 Standards and metadata	18
2.4.3 Data sharing	18
2.4.4 Archiving and preservation	18
2.5 Microbial investigations dataset	18
2.5.1 Dataset description	18
2.5.2 Standards and metadata	19
2.5.3 Data sharing	19
2.5.4 Archiving and preservation	19
2.6 Effects on the crew dataset.....	19
2.6.1 Dataset description	19
2.6.2 Standards and metadata	20
2.6.3 Data sharing	20
2.6.4 Archiving and preservation	20
3 Data management plan updates	21
References	22

Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
AWI	Alfred-Wegener-Institute of polar and marine research	H2020	Horizon 2020
CNR	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	LED	Light emitting diode
DLO	Stichting Dienst Landbouwkundig Onderzoek	LIT	Limerick Institute of Technology
DLR	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V.	MTF	Mobile test facility
DLR-RY	DLR - Institut für Raumfahrtssysteme	RD	Research data
DLR-ME	DLR - Institut für Luft- und Raumfahrtmedizin	SP	Scientific publication
DMP	Data management plan	TBC	To be confirmed
E-Nose	Electronic nose	TBD	To be determined
EC	Electrical conductivity	UoG	University of Guelph
EDEN	Evolution and Design of Environmentally-closed Nutrition-sources	WLGS	Wireless group structure
EU	European Union	WP	Work package
FP	Framework Programme		

1 General EDEN ISS data management guidelines

This introductory section reviews the overall guidelines that structure how scientific publications and research data will be managed within the EDEN ISS project. Although this document discusses certain aspects related to scientific publications, the data management plan (DMP) primarily focuses on how research data is managed over the course of the project.

1.1 Linkages to relevant Horizon 2020 guidelines

Several Horizon 2020 guidelines and EDEN ISS specific project documents were consulted in the generation of the DMP for the EDEN ISS project. The overarching guidelines of the EDEN ISS DMP follow that of the June 2013 G8 Science Ministers' Statement on open scientific research in that, "open scientific research data should be easily discoverable, accessible, assessable, intelligible, useable, and wherever possible interoperable to specific quality standards". The project has agreed to participate in the Pilot on Open Research Data in Horizon 2020 and uses the specific Horizon 2020 guidelines associated with 'open' access [1] to ensure that project results provide the greatest impact possible. The format of the developed EDEN ISS DMP follows that format suggested within the *Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020* [2]. Figure 1 provides a summary of the relevant references and important considerations used to draft the EDEN ISS DMP.

Figure 1: Relevant references and important considerations that were utilized in the development of the EDEN ISS data management plan. Indicated for each of the listed references is if it deals with scientific publications (SP), research data (RD) or both.

As is evident in Figure 1 in addition to the relevant reference documents, the EDEN ISS DMP is influenced by the repositories available to the EDEN ISS consortium and the types of datasets that will be collected. Additionally, the DMP, from its outset, it considered to be a plan that will evolve over the duration of the project as project goals are further refined and potentially new dataset types are elucidated.

1.2 Guideline distinctions between scientific publications and research data

It is important to note that this DMP describes how project research data will be handled during and after the research project. Although not distinct, the DMP does not explicitly detail (at length) the management of project scientific publications. Instead, the Horizon 2020 guidelines specific to scien-

tific publications and with direct relevance to the EDEN ISS project consortium have been summarized here:

Scientific publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each beneficiary <i>must</i> ensure open access (free of charge, online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results [1, 3]. • Scientific publications (including associated metadata) <i>must</i> be deposited into an online repository for scientific publications (a project website does not suffice for this purpose). <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Note: Depositing of the scientific publication into a repository ('green' open access) <i>must</i> still be conducted in the case when 'gold' open access (publishing in a scientific journal) is chosen. • Ensure open access to the scientific publication (published article or final peer-reviewed manuscript) no later than: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or ○ within six months in any other case (note that six months is shorter than a wide range of subscription journal embargo periods (typically 12 – 24 months) and thus this eliminates this as a route for providing open access). • In addition to the mandate on open access to peer-reviewed publications, partners are strongly encouraged to provide open access to other types of scientific publications (e.g. non-peer-reviewed publications), including books, conference proceedings and grey literature (informally published written material not controlled by scientific publishers, e.g. reports). • Prior notice of any planned publications shall be given to the other EDEN consortium partners at least 30 calendar days before publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the Coordinator and to the consortium partners proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the stated time limit, the publication is permitted. • Published results shall at a minimum (although also a preference to display the EU emblem) include the following statement demonstrating EU support [3]: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ <i>"This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 636501"</i>. ○ Please see a later section of the DMP (or the EDEN ISS Grant Agreement) for scientific publication metadata information that must be entered into the repository. • <i>Misconceptions about open access to scientific publications. In the context of research funding, open access requirements in no way imply an obligation to publish results. The decision on whether or not to publish lies entirely with the fundees. Open access becomes an issue only if publication is elected as a means of dissemination [1].</i> • In addition to the more traditional scientific publications generated by the project, project deliverables and other relevant reports will also be deposited within an open access repository to the extent possible.
-------------------------	--

When questions arise, the EDEN ISS Grant Agreement should be referenced for legally binding aspects related to EDEN ISS project scientific publications.

The research data referred to in this DMP is specifically the *underlying data, including its associated metadata, needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications*. Horizon 2020 documentation defines research data as [1]:

...information, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered and as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images.

With respect to the underlying research data the following overarching guidelines (non-comprehensive) are important for EDEN ISS partners to note:

Research Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EDEN ISS has agreed to participate in the Horizon 2020 <i>Open Research Data Pilot</i>. This pilot aims to improve and maximize access to and the reuse of generated research data. This implies that the project partners should attempt to make these datasets as accessible and openly available as possible. It is worthwhile to note that it is expected that the depositing of datasets in this open access manner will likely become the norm in the future just as open access publications are themselves becoming the norm and as an open access pilot on scientific publications was conducted during FP7 from which it became a requirement within Horizon 2020. • Although there is no legal obligation to do so, the consortium must also aim to deposit in an open access manner the ‘research data needed to validate the scientific results’ [4]. • The datasets should be deposited in a research data repository measures taken to make it possible for any user to access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate the data free of charge [4]. • Open access data shall at a minimum (although also a preference to display the EU emblem) include the following statement demonstrating EU support (with relevant information included into the repository metadata) [3]: • <i>“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 636501”</i>.
----------------------	---

As described in the *Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020* there is a strong desire to deposit underlying research data. *“This requirement is based on the fact that the concept of ‘publication’ has rapidly evolved over the past years and in the context of the digital era. Therefore, the notion of ‘publication’ increasingly includes the data underpinning the publication and results presented, also referred to as ‘underlying’ data. This data is needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publication and is therefore seen as a crucial part of the publication and an important ingredient enabling scientific best practise”*.

1.3 Top-level EDEN ISS data management implementation

The DMP details what data the project will generate, whether and how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and re-use, and how it will be curated and preserved. These items are addressed for each specific dataset that the EDEN ISS project expects to generate.

1.3.1 Expected project datasets

A summary of the top-level EDEN ISS project datasets are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Top-level EDEN ISS project datasets.

Name of Dataset	Included Data	Involved WPs
Plant cultivation experiments and training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Growth chamber environment data • Plant specific data (appearance and measurements) • Logistics data (demands, labour, training) 	WP 2.2; WP 4.2
Mobile Test Facility operations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental data • System health data • Logistics data • Imaging data 	WP 4.4; WP 5
Full-rack demonstrator operations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental data • System health data • Logistics data 	WP 4.1; WP 4.4; WP 5

Food quality and safety	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chemical and foreign matter quantification and nutrient analysis of food crops • Daily nutrient dietary supply from food crop • Biological screening of infectious agents and microbial contaminants • Non-biological contaminant determination • Crew subjective assessments (palatability, flavour and texture) • Required crew time • Training time • Images 	WP 4.2; WP 4.4; WP 5.4;
Microbial investigations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Images (sampling locations, samples) • Microbial counts • Microbial identification • E-Nose results • Comparison of 'traditional' and E-Nose results 	WP 3.5; WP 4.4; WP 5.6
Effects on the crew	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaires • Simulator/learning program output • Wireless crew member tracking data 	WP 5.5

This document has been organized with each subsequent section addressing a different project dataset. It should be noted that this document is a 'living document' in that as additional project datasets are identified, or their contents are further refined, the DMP will be correspondingly updated.

1.3.2 Standards and metadata

Metadata is 'data about data'. Its purpose in the context of Horizon 2020 is to enable data users to find generated research data (as well as scientific publications) and to acknowledge EU funding. The latter, also serving as a mechanism to better permit the monitoring of scientific output of Horizon 2020 in general.

The following lists the minimum fields of metadata that should accompany an EDEN ISS project generated scientific publication in a repository [4]:

- The terms: "European Union (EU)", "Horizon 2020"
- Name of the action (Research and Innovation Action)
- Acronym and grant number (EDEN ISS, 636501)
- Publication date
- Length of embargo period if applicable
- Persistent identifier

Due to the nature of research data its metadata requires additional details which often include (repository and subject dependent):

- Title of the dataset
- Name(s) of dataset creator(s)
- Description of data
- Source of data
- Creation date
- Spatial coverage of dataset
- Temporal coverage of dataset
- Format
- Language
- Location of data
- Digital object identifier (assigned by the repository)
- Access status and embargo
- License
- Funding statement

- Related publications
- Dataset citation

In all instances, when providing metadata for research data it is important to imagine a secondary data user attempting to make sense of the data in your absence. Any information necessary or helpful to this secondary data user should be considered by the dataset creator as important elements to add to the repository metadata.

1.3.3 Data sharing

The repository should also include information regarding the software, tools and instruments that were utilized by the dataset creator(s) so that secondary data users can access and then validate the results. The EDEN ISS consortium will strive to make many of the collected datasets open access. When this is not the case, the data sharing section for that particular dataset will describe why access has been restricted. In regards to the specific repositories available to the EDEN ISS consortium, numerous project partners maintain institutional repositories (Table 2) where project scientific publications and in some instances, research data will be deposited. The utilization of a specific repository will depend primarily on the primary creator of the publication/data in question.

Table 2: EDEN ISS available institutional repositories.

Project Partner	Repository Name
AWI	ePIC
CNR	ArchEnviMat
DLR	elib
DLO	Wageningen Yield
UoG	Atrium

The other project partners do not operate publically accessible institutional repositories (although numerous partners operate internal repositories) and when depositing scientific publications will utilize either a discipline specific repository or utilize the EU recommended service OpenAIRE (<http://www.openaire.eu>) as an initial step to finding resources to determine relevant repositories. Project research data will be deposited to the online data repository Zenodo (<http://zenodo.org/>). Zenodo is a free service developed by CERN under the EU FP7 project OpenAIREplus (grant agreement no. 283595).

The EDEN ISS Zenodo collection can be accessed here: <https://zenodo.org/collection/user-edeniss>

In summary, as a baseline EDEN ISS partners will deposit:

Scientific publications – on their respective institute repositories in addition (when relevant) to the EDEN ISS Zenodo repository

Project deliverables – to the EDEN ISS Zenodo collection (when possible)

Research data – to the EDEN ISS Zenodo collection (when possible)

Other project output files – to the EDEN ISS Zenodo collection (when relevant)

When depositing EDEN ISS project publications, deliverables and data to the Zenodo, the information included in Figure 2 should be entered into the online information associated with each deposited object.

Figure 2: Information to be included for all items deposited to the EDEN ISS Zenodo collection/repository.

1.3.4 Archiving and preservation

The bulk of early project work (e.g. work packages 1 to 3) will initially be saved on the specifically involved consortium member data servers. All data relevant to the integrated project success or upon completion of defined processed/organized datasets will be also stored on central DLR-RY data servers. Indeed, data servers at DLR-RY will serve as the central repository for shared project data. A custom Sharepoint server (EDEN ISS teamsite) has been configured and is already operational being used by the EDEN ISS consortium (Figure 3). The deposited data available to project partners is accessible through a password protected connection. Data and all EDEN ISS project information on this project server is regularly backed up as per nominal DLR-RY data security measures (once every 24 hours).

Figure 3: Screen capture of the main menu of the EDEN ISS Sharepoint collaborative site.

In addition to the EDEN ISS Sharepoint server, the aforementioned institutional repositories as well as the Zenodo online data repository, provide large volume storage capacity and meet important archiving and preservation Horizon 2020 requirements.

2 Project datasets

The following sections detail the expected EDEN ISS project datasets and their management over the EDEN ISS project.

2.1 Plant cultivation experiments and training dataset

2.1.1 Dataset description

A large dataset associated with the growth of the selected crops destined for the EDEN ISS mobile test facility (MTF) in Antarctic will be generated during laboratory tests in WP 2.2. The DLO led plant cultivation experiments will better characterize the growth of the selected plant species under nearly identical environmental, horticultural management and plant growth support hardware parameters as those to be used in the completed MTF/Antarctica. Such experiments conducted with the approximately five selected plant species (selected based upon a detailed assessment conducted earlier in the same work package) will have a duration of several months. The following data will be compiled:

Plant cultivation experiments and training dataset	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experimental configuration (utilized hardware, software, operations/horticultural management procedures). Such items include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Time experiment commenced, time when the experimental configuration was modified, time the experiment was concluded ○ Labour requirements (time) ○ Experiment set-points (temperature, humidity, photoperiod, irrigation frequency etc.) • Growth chamber environmental data (e.g. air temperature, humidity, ppCO₂, ppO₂, photoperiod, light intensity, light quality (spectra), nutrient solution temperature, pH, electrical conductivity (logged on a 1 min frequency throughout the experiment)). • Plant specific data: appearance (written observations), images (collected on a regular basis), relative growth rate, leaf area index, leaf area, plant height, fresh mass, dry mass, % dry mass. • Logistics data: demands (e.g. power, water nutrient, CO₂), labour requirements (management, harvesting), training time and content requirements.
--	---

All data from each single plant species trial (e.g. the growth of one plant species type over a fixed duration ranging from e.g. 1 to 4 month) will be output and subsequently stored into a single large tab-delimited text file (e.g. output from the EDEN ISS nominally utilized Microsoft Excel data file). The only exception is the collected image files which themselves will be stored individually in .JPEG format with each image including a filename indicating the time it was collected (e.g. YYYY-MM-DD-TIME- format) as well as physical position (if relevant) within the experiment. Also related are summarized cultivation recipes for the studied crops.

Similar datasets with respect to the influence of various environmental treatments on different plant species do exist in the literature and thus the collected datasets will be of interest to secondary users. It is expected that several scientific publications (approximately two) will stem from this project work package. Initial effort will be placed on making these publications as comprehensive and as useful as possible. The publications will themselves serve as a useful reference for secondary dataset users as they will elaborate in great detail the data collection scheme, tools and processing methodology. Numerous raw datasets will also be made available.

2.1.2 Standards and metadata

The primary dataset contained in the tab-delimited text file will contain detailed comments with each measurement column being specifically described. Information such as sensor types, reported units and misc. clarification will be provided so that a 'secondary' data user with no prior knowledge of the conducted experiments can understand all data elements. A separate graphic (or several

graphics) will also be provided that will display the specific layout of the greenhouse/growth chamber growth trials. Sensor locations will be illustrated in detail. The tab-delimited text file format implies that no specific software is required to access it. A similar comment can be made with regard to the JPEG file format for collected images (as well as described layout/configuration graphics).

2.1.3 Data sharing

Primary data will be published in one or more open access scientific journals. These publications will also be deposited within DLO's *Wageningen Yield* institutional repository (OpenAIRE compliant). Select full datasets will also be deposited to the EDEN ISS Zenodo collection (in addition to potentially depositing this data to certified Dutch data repositories DANS EASY or 3TU.Datacentrum) and be made fully available to the public. No special access requirements or tools will be required.

2.1.4 Archiving and preservation

Datasets will be initially saved on Wageningen data servers. These servers are backed up as per institutional guidelines. No costs are associated with this institutional archiving and preservation service. Datasets deposited to either DANS EASY or 3TU.Datacentrum implies that the dataset will be accessible and readable for at least 10 years.

2.2 Mobile Test Facility operations dataset

2.2.1 Dataset description

This dataset stems from two separate operational phases with the integrated MTF. The first, during the test deployment phase conducted at DLR Bremen in mid-2017 and the second, during the primary operational phase in Antarctica from early 2018 to the end of the year. This implies that this operational data will be collected during WP 4.4 and WP 5 (numerous sub-work packages). During these phases, the overall MTF environmental data (in the airlock, service section and future exploration greenhouse), system health as well as imaging data will be collected. The following data parameters will be collected (approximate counts of distinct measurements/sensors included in brackets):

Mobile Test Facility operations dataset	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Temperatures (>30), humidity (>10), ppCO₂ (4), ppO₂ (2), light level (8), pH (3), EC (3), nutrient ion activities (3), reservoir levels (4), air flow (4), liquid flow rates (8), door switch (3). • System health data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Actuator ON/OFF commanding (e.g. pumps, fans, valves, LEDs, etc.) (>50) • Logistics data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Operations performed, crew time, failures detected, time to resolve failures, consumables, operational difficulties, etc. (collected on an opportunistic basis) • Imaging <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Plant health images (visual, fluorescent and infrared), nominal internal images
--	---

Environmental and system health data will be collected on a sampling rate of approximately once per second and logged at a rate of once per 10 seconds. Visual imaging data will be collected at a frequency of approximately once per minute, while fluorescent and infrared data will be collected on an opportunistic/irregular basis.

It is expected that these environmental and operational datasets will be useful to secondary users as there will be interest to compare the operations of the EDEN ISS MTF to other analogue or extreme environment plant production systems (e.g. other Antarctic, Arctic or remote-site plant production systems/greenhouses).

2.2.2 Standards and metadata

The primary dataset contained in the tab-delimited text file will contain detailed comments with each measurement column being specifically described. Information such as sensor types, reported units and misc. clarification will be provided so that a secondary data user with no prior knowledge of the conducted experiments can understand all data elements. A separate graphic (or several graphics) will also be provided that will display the specific layout of the MTF. Sensor locations will be illustrated in detail. The tab-delimited text file format implies that no specific software is required to access it. A similar comment can be made with regard to the JPEG file format for collected images (as well as described layout/configuration graphics).

2.2.3 Data sharing

Primary data will be published in one or more open access scientific journals. These publications will also be deposited within the DLR's *elib* institutional repository (OpenAIRE compliant) in addition to project deliverables being deposited to the EDEN ISS Zenodo collection. The full environmental datasets as well as visual plant health imaging sets will also be deposited within the Zenodo and be made fully available to the public. No special access requirements or tools will be required.

2.2.4 Archiving and preservation

The WP 4.4 (on-site DLR Bremen test program) datasets will be saved to DLR data servers. These servers are backed up on a once a day frequency. The WP 5 datasets will be initially stored to a local computer within the MTF as well as a larger server within the Neumayer Station III. These will be the primary repositories for the data during the Antarctica demonstration phase. Regular backups of the MTF local computer (once every two days) will occur via the connection of an external hard-drive. This hard-drive will otherwise be stored within the Neumayer Station III. A subset of the comprehensive environmental and system health data (e.g. a line of data every 10 minutes) will be transferred to Europe on a regular basis. A subset of the collected imaging data will be transmitted as satellite bandwidth permits. This downloaded data will be saved to DLR data servers and backed up a once a day frequency. Following the completion of the Antarctic demonstration phase, the full collected dataset will also be transferred to the DLR data servers. No additional costs are associated with this DLR institutional archiving and preservation service. Depositing a large subset of this data to Zenodo will also aid in archiving and preservation.

2.3 Full-rack demonstrator operations dataset

2.3.1 Dataset description

This dataset stems from three separate operational phases with the full-rack demonstrator plant growth system. The first, collected during development and test phase conducted at TAS-I (Turin) in mid-2016 to early-2017. The second collected during the test deployment phase conducted at DLR Bremen in mid-2017 and the third collected during the primary operational phase in Antarctica from early 2018 to the end of the year. This implies that this operational data will be collected during WP 4.1, WP 4.4 and WP 5 (numerous sub-work packages). During these phases, the overall full-rack demonstrator environmental data, system health as well as imaging data will be collected. The following research data will be collected:

Full-rack demonstrator operations dataset	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Air temperature, RH, ppCO₂, ppO₂; nutrient solution/substrate EC, pH, nutrient solution temperature. • System health data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Pumps/valves ON/OFF conditions; light temperatures, voltages, ON/OFF conditions; cooling water temperature. • Logistics data <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Operations performed, crew time, failures detected, time to resolve failures, consumables, operational difficulties, etc. <p>Access to some MTF environmental parameters (i.e. temperature, RH, ppCO₂, ppO₂) of the container will also be collected to permit the calculation of mass balances.</p>
--	---

Environmental and system health data will be collected on a sampling rate of approximately once per second and logged at a rate of once per 10 seconds (TBC).

2.3.2 Standards and metadata

The primary dataset contained in tab-delimited text files will contain detailed comments with each measurement column being specifically described. Information such as sensor types, reported units and misc. clarification will be provided so that a secondary data user with no prior knowledge of the conducted experiments can understand all data elements. A separate graphic (or several graphics) will also be provided that will display the specific layout of the full-rack demonstrator. Sensor locations will be illustrated in detail. The tab-delimited text file format implies that no specific software is required to access it.

2.3.3 Data sharing

All internal design details of the full-rack demonstrator will be kept internally (TAS-I). General performance and test results will be published in journal and conference papers to the extent possible. TAS-I generated scientific publications will initially be submitted to an internal online repository but will also be made available in an open source manner as per Horizon 2020 guidelines. With respect to the datasets themselves, TAS-I will strive to make a subset of the data open source. These will be made open source via the EDEN ISS Zenodo collection.

2.3.4 Archiving and preservation

During the test phases in Turin and Bremen data will be downloaded from the full-rack demonstrator data acquisition system to a laptop on a weekly (TBC) basis. Data files will be uploaded weekly (TBC) to TAS-I's on-line data repository (WAND system), which itself is backed up on multiple servers. During the Antarctic campaign, data will be automatically downloaded from the full-rack demonstrator data acquisition system and saved to the local computer within the MTF and to a larger server within the Neumayer Station III. A subset of the comprehensive environmental and system health data (e.g. a line of data every 10 minutes) will be transferred to Europe on a regular basis. This downloaded data will be saved to DLR and TAS-I data servers and backed up a once a day frequency. Following the completion of the Antarctic demonstration phase, the full collected dataset will also be transferred to the TAS-I data servers. No additional costs are associated with this institutional archiving and preservation service. Depositing a TBD subset of this data to Zenodo will also aid in archiving and preservation.

2.4 Food quality and safety dataset

2.4.1 Dataset description

The procedures for testing a) food quality, b) food safety and c) post-harvest processing defined in WP 2.5 will be tested on plant material which will be produced in respective labs of CNR and LIT under protocols WP 4.2. Food quality will be assessed both in terms of chemical composition and in terms of consumer perception. Standard methods will be used to fully characterize the plant tissues and

organs that will compose the food (and waste) fractions of the cultivation outputs. The main focus will be on carbohydrates (chemical species, digestible and indigestible fractions), proteins (quantity and amino acid composition), organic acids (including Vitamin C), fat, carbon /nitrogen ratio, compounds with anti-nutritional effects (e.g. oxalic acid, nitrate), nutraceutical properties (e.g. polyphenols, pro-vitamins, fibre) and mineral composition. Nutritional and nutraceutical values for each crop will be output. Results, including those from proxy measurements procedures (e.g. for non-destructive quality estimation) will be recorded. The above measurements conducted during laboratory and pre-Antarctic assembly, integration and test phase in Bremen (based upon in-situ analysis as well as shipment to LIT and CNR laboratories) will be followed by a small subset of similar measurements (determined based upon pre-Antarctic results and with focus on non-destructive means) conducted during the Antarctic test phase.

The food quality and safety dataset (LIT, CNR) includes images collected over the duration of the project. These images will be stored individually in .JPEG format with each image including a filename indicating the time it was collected (e.g. YYYY-MM-DD-TIME- format) as well details on the sample in question. Post-processed images and text data files summarizing quantification results from these images (image analysis, colour assessment) will be output.

Microbial monitoring data (CNR) will be compiled during plant growth and prior to crew consumption. Data will be collected during the overall system assembly, integration and test phase as well as during the Antarctic demonstration phase (with some samples returned from Antarctica). Specific data will include: total microbial colony count; microbial colony differential and identification.

LIT will evaluate the effects of post-harvest processing protocols for each crop by developing a sensory profile validated via a trained sensory panel. The profile will include visual appearance and colour variance, smell, taste and texture analysis. The post-harvest processing and storage protocols will be compared and scored via descriptive analysis. Waste plant tissue composition will be evaluated in order to define its mass and quality in terms of processing and disposal.

The required training time and crew time required for the use of all analytical equipment employed within the food quality, safety and processing associated work packages and operational phases will be logged and compiled within tab-delimited text files (e.g. output from Excel). A text file based output including the results of the comparison of the selected food quality and safety methods/technologies (CNR) will also be generated. The following is a summary of the research data associated with this dataset:

Food quality and safety dataset	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chemical and foreign matter quantification and nutrient analysis of food crops <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Data from analytical measurement of plant and nutrient solution composition will be collected including datasets from Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy; Ion Chromatography, Liquid Chromatography – Mass Spectroscopy; UV/Visible Spectroscopy and Gas Chromatography. Other datasets will be generated from analysis of % Carbon: Hydrogen: Oxygen ratios; Total Organic Carbon and %Biomass. • Daily nutrient dietary supply from food crop <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ % Proteins; Carbohydrates; Fats; essential minerals and vitamins • Biological screening of infectious agents and microbial contaminants <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Datasets from Biological Oxygen Demand and Carbon Oxygen Demand Analysis on Nutrient Solution; Total Microbial Count; Microbial Differentiation and identification. • Non-biological contaminant determination <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Liquid Chromatography – Mass Spectroscopy for identification of any chemical contaminant. • Crew subjective assessments (palatability, flavour and texture) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Crew ability to differentiate between sensory panel assessment factors such as taste indicators: bitter / bland; sour / sweet; sharp / smooth; and visual perception. • Required crew time • Training time • Images <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Post-Harvest Plant Health; Sensory Panel Training; Sensory Panel Food Plates; Microbial Cultures; sample preparation and analysis.
--	---

2.4.2 Standards and metadata

Data associated with chemical and foreign matter; nutrient analysis; palatability, flavor and texture; required crew time and training time will be saved within tab-delimited text files contained detailed comments with each measurement column being specifically described. Suitable information on measurement tools, methodology, sensory panel will be included. The use of the tab-delimited text file format implies that no specific software is required to access them. In all instances, analytical data will be treated with conventional scientific approaches (such as statistical evaluation, compare and contrast tests with existing literature data, expression as table and graphs) in order to make them available to other project partners and eventually for the international technical and scientific community.

2.4.3 Data sharing

Primary data will be published in one or more open access scientific journals (LIT, CNR). CNR publications will also be deposited within CNR's *ArchEnviMat* institutional repository. LIT publications will be included on the research websites of the associated researchers but also published in an open access online repository. Selected full datasets will also be deposited within the EDEN ISS Zenodo collection and be made fully available to the public. No special access requirements or tools will be required.

2.4.4 Archiving and preservation

Final datasets will be saved onto LIT and CNR data servers. These data servers are regularly backed up as per institutional guidelines. No costs are associated with this institutional archiving and preservation service.

2.5 Microbial investigations dataset

2.5.1 Dataset description

DLR-ME will assess the microbial environment inside the MTF by the analysis of samples taken from surfaces. To obtain a broad overview of the diversity and physiological capability of cultivable micro-

organisms, different growth conditions will be used: e.g. different temperatures, oligotrophic and copiotrophic media, aerobic and anaerobic conditions targeting at aerobic mesophiles, heat-tolerant mesophiles, psychrophiles/psychrotolerants, oligotrophs, mesophilic fungi, and anaerobes. Selected isolates will be identified based on 16S and 18S rRNA gene sequence analyses. In addition to cultivation, the phylogenetic diversity of the uncultivable organisms from selected samples will be determined by community profiling (denaturing gradient gel electrophoresis), 16S and 18S rRNA gene analyses via PCR, cloning and sequencing. Microbial population dynamics will be followed by the analysis of samples from the MTF taken at different points in time at the beginning, during and at the end of the operational phase. The sampling activities of WP 5.6 will be conducted partly in parallel to the utilization of the E-Nose system (WP 3.5) so that results of these complimentary approaches can be compared directly under real conditions. Samples and images will also be conducted during overall system assembly, integration and test (WP 4.4) in Bremen. Results from laboratory testing and training of the E-Nose (odour profiles) will also be collected. The following is a summary of the research data associated with this dataset:

Microbial investigations dataset	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For the various sampling locations and time points: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Images of sampling locations and samples ○ Environmental parameters inside the MTF ○ Counts of colony forming units after growth under different conditions ○ Identification of selected isolates based on 16S and 18S rRNA gene analyses ○ Community profiling by the molecular analysis (selected samples) ○ Comparison to E-Nose results, if available. • E-Nose data
---	---

2.5.2 Standards and metadata

Images will be stored individually in .JPEG format with each image including a filename indicating the time it was collected (e.g. YYYY-MM-DD-TIME- format) as well as physical position within the MTF. The description of the specific samples as well as the quantitative results of the performed analyses will be saved within a tab-delimited text file (e.g. generated from Excel) with sufficient comments and labelling to permit reuse/future use.

2.5.3 Data sharing

Primary data will be published in one or more open access scientific journals (DLR-ME, Airbus Defence and Space). These publications will also be deposited within the DLR's *elib* institutional repository (OpenAIRE compliant). Following publication, a large subset of the nominal research data will also be deposited within the EDEN ISS Zenodo collection and be made fully available to the public. No special access requirements or tools will be required.

2.5.4 Archiving and preservation

Sampling location images, some sample photographs, E-Nose data and MTF environmental data will initially be saved to Neumayer Station III data servers before transmission by satellite and saving to DLR servers. Final storage of all dataset data and images will be conducted on secure and regularly backed up DLR data servers (DLR-ME).

2.6 Effects on the crew dataset

2.6.1 Dataset description

It is of highest relevance to monitor crewmember mood, workability and cohesion to ensure the mission success and the functionality of the MTF. DLR-ME will assess mood by standard questionnaires (e.g. profile of mood states, computerized, running on the "6df"-Notebook). Workability will be monitored by a long-term self-sufficient learning program ("6df", Notebook, two hand controls, simulator and learning program for hand controlled flying and docking a spacecraft with six degrees of freedom, tested during Mars500). Crew cohesion will be monitored by a Wireless Group Structure sys-

tem (WLGS, Notebook + Base station, individual satellites for each crew member and central locations, tested during Mars500), registering the time spent together. Additionally the time will be registered, spent near the plants in opposite to a neutral control place (to be defined during the project). The specific effect of fresh food could be assessed, if it is not continuously provided (as assumed) and the measurement points of mood and Wireless Group Structure system are coordinated with the fresh food days. All data assessment is based on computerized methods, storing all relevant data in an automated way. The preparation of the WLGS-System (charging, distributing satellites, data download) needs a responsible partner within the crew. For “6df” and WLGS hardware check www.koralewski.de.

Report and data will be provided in an anonymized matter (agreed within the project). Extraordinary events will be summarized. A common evaluation of crew development and individual wellness will be given. Data matrix Time – individual psychological mood; Data matrix Time – individual learn progress; Data matrix Time – crew cohesion, single crew member involvement. The aforementioned datasets are associated with WP 5.5. The following is a summary of the research data associated with this dataset:

Effects on the crew dataset	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaires • Simulator/learning program output • Wireless crew member tracking data
-----------------------------	---

2.6.2 Standards and metadata

Good practise and standards will be utilized in the collection of the effects on the crew / psychological datasets so as to ensure its usability while maintaining privacy etc.

2.6.3 Data sharing

Primary data will be published in one or more open access scientific journals. These publications will also be deposited within the DLR’s *elib* institutional repository (OpenAIRE compliant). It is not planned to release the raw effects of the crew /psychological datasets so as to better address privacy concerns.

2.6.4 Archiving and preservation

Questionnaire datasets will be saved to DLR data servers. These servers are backed up on a once a day frequency. Simulator/learning program data will be saved locally on Neumayer Station III servers using coded system only known by the principal investigator (i.e. to maintain privacy). This data will be transmitted through the Neumayer Station III satellite link and subsequently stored on the same DLR servers at DLR-ME (secure and regularly backed up). A similar system will be used to store the wireless crew member tracking data. No additional costs are associated with this DLR institutional archiving and preservation service.

3 Data management plan updates

At least two updates will be made to the DMP over the course of the project. These will be based upon the fact that the EDEN ISS project generated data and its potential uses will be further defined as the project progresses. At a minimum, a new version of the DMP will be completed by the mid-term of the project and subsequently by the final review.

References

- [1] "Guidelines on Open Access to Scientific Publications and Research Data in Horizon 2020," Version 1.0, 11 December 2013.
- [2] "Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020," Version 1.0, 11 December 2013.
- [3] "EDEN ISS Grant Agreement," Grant Agreement Number: 636501, Article 38.
- [4] "EDEN ISS Grant Agreement," Grant Agreement Number: 636501, Article 29.